

Non-exponential Decay and Growth *via* Tsallis Statistics

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Abstract

We introduce a new one-parameter model, derived from Tsallis statistics, which adheres to the half-life condition. This innovative function is referred to as the q -Decay constant. Building on this concept, we also present the Eastmond Non-Extensive Decay Modulator (Eastmond-NEDM), a metric designed to quantify how non-extensivity (q) influences decay and growth dynamics. The q -Decay constant is subsequently incorporated into a growth and decay equation for various randomly chosen q values, while utilizing arbitrary half-lives. For the growth scenario, a particular case of the Bateman equation is considered, where the mean lifetime is infinite, corresponding to a stable daughter nuclide. Both studies are conducted within the superadditive/subadditive regimes, i.e., where the q -parameter satisfies $q < 1$ and $q > 1$, respectively. Multiple real-world examples are provided to substantiate the theoretical framework.

Keywords: half-life, Bateman equation, Tsallis statistics, radioactive decay

MSC Classification: 62P35 , 82D99

1 Introduction

It is a well-known fact that the rate of radioactive decay is first order. Moreover, reaction rates have been studied extensively throughout the scientific literature[1–3]. To be specific, Tsallis q -logarithm applied to reaction rates was studied in ref.[4].However, bear in mind that the so-called rate constant in chemical kinetics is not the same as the radioactive decay constant. At the

fundamental level they do not share anything in common. The first can be used to make predictions and the second is totally probabilistic. Nevertheless, radioactivity occurs when an isotope has a *half-life* much greater than the K-shell vacancy *half-life* of carbon[5, 6]. K-shell vacancies result in K-shell activity which can be characterized by K-capture; described by $p + e^- \rightarrow n + \nu_e$. The atomic nucleus emits a particle as a consequence of K-capture—a proton rich nucleus captures an electron from the $n = 1$ shell or K-shell[7]. This process leads to X-ray emission when electrons transition from energy levels $n > 1$ down to the principal quantum number $n = 1$. Or Auger electrons[8], which are emitted when an outer electron fills a vacancy in the innermost electron shell.

Hereinafter, we will adopt the term “nuclide” in lieu of “isotope”—because of the distinction between the terms isotope and nuclide. We classify nuclides as: Isotopes (having the same # of protons); Isotones (having the same # of neutrons); and Isobars (having the same # of nucleons)[9]. Furthermore, this study is inspired/motivated by the recent emergence of the q -decay constant, a novel concept with promising implications for modeling radioactive decay processes. Note that its inclusion offers new avenues for modeling non-exponential decay and anomalous dynamical processes.

1.1 Objective

Our investigation will center entirely on the mathematical constant describing the rate of radioactive decay. And so, we will consider a more general case of the logarithm which connects the decay constant and *half-life* for some randomly chosen nuclides (note, this idea is newfangled). In particular, we will concentrate on radioactive decay and growth, respectively. We shall call this new modified function, the q -Decay constant (see Eq.(58)). Hence:

- By incorporating the parameter “ q ”, we alter the radioactive decay constant through the application of Tsallis q -logarithm[10]. This modification ultimately leads to the development of the Eastmond Nonextensive Decay Modulator, which is constructed within Sections (2-3).
- Subsequently, we plot and analyze a set of miscellaneous (superextensive [superadditive]/subextensive) q -values for radioactive decay, and accumulation of stable daughter nuclide, using the q -Decay constant in Section (4).
- Also, we examine property preservation and branching decay in Section (5).
- Our final conclusions are presented in Section (6).

2 Tsallis Nonextensive Statistical Mechanics

The Boltzmann-Gibbs (BG) entropy for a set of discrete states— Ω —is given by

$$S_{BG} = -k \sum_{i=1}^{\Omega} p_i \ln p_i, \quad (1)$$

where p_i is the probability of the i th microstate and the sum of all p_i is equal to unity. And when $k = k_B$ —the Boltzmann constant—thermostatistics becomes the dominant feature of interest. Additionally, for equal probabilities, i.e., $p_i = 1/\Omega, \forall i$, the new entropy is

$$S_{BG} = k \ln \Omega. \quad (2)$$

Now for any two independent subsystems Q^α and Q^γ —from probability theory it is well-known that their probabilities can be factorized. And because we can factor their probabilities, the Boltzmann-Gibbs entropy is additive, hence

$$S_q(Q^\alpha + Q^\gamma) = S_q(Q^\alpha) + S_q(Q^\gamma). \quad (3)$$

A system which exhibits thermal equilibrium with a thermostat at temperature T has a Boltzmann-Gibbs weight which is defined as

$$p_i = \frac{e^{-\beta E_i}}{Z_{BG}}, \quad (4)$$

where $\beta = \frac{1}{kT}$ and

$$Z_{BG} = \sum_{j=1}^{\Omega} e^{-\beta E_j}. \quad (5)$$

The term Z_{BG} is a normalization factor whose primary function is to correct the probabilities; and is mostly often referred to as the partition function. The term E_j in the exponent of Eq.(5) denotes the energy spectrum. These concepts constitute the essential framework upon which BG statistical mechanics is built.

Tsallis nonextensive statistical mechanics[11] was developed on the general principles of BG statistical mechanics. The term *nonextensive* as applied here to nonextensive statistical mechanics arises from the fact that independent systems—for example Q^α and Q^γ —are not additive, under certain conditions. In other words, the probability of two independent systems Q^α and Q^γ , for an entropic parameter of value $q \neq 1$ is nonadditive. Hence, the name nonextensive—nonadditive—statistical mechanics is given to the theory. Note, the entropic parameter (q) is a measure of the nonadditivity in the system[12]. Moreover, let it be noted that S_q appears to describe systems that exhibit weak chaos. Such systems adhere to a null *Lyapunov exponent* (λ), where $\lambda \approx \frac{1}{n} \ln \left(\frac{|\delta(t)|}{|\delta_0|} \right)$. Here, $\delta(t)$ and δ_0 are the separation and initial vector lengths associated with an attractor[13], and n is the number of iterations.

In Nonadditive statistical mechanics the BG entropy S_{BG} is extremized ($S_{q \neq 1}$) and in the limit as the entropic parameter $q \rightarrow 1$, the ordinary BG entropy is obtained[14, 15]. The entropic parameter q , is determined by the microscopic dynamics of the system and is characterized by the degree of nonadditivity in the said system. In addition, if Q^α and Q^γ are two independent

systems then from probability theory it must be true that $p(Q^\alpha + Q^\gamma) = p(Q^\alpha)p(Q^\gamma)$. But entropy is nonnegative so $S_q \geq 0$ —Tsallis entropy—and so for $q < 1$ we have the superadditivity condition or superextensivity.

Furthermore, for $q = 1$, we have additivity or extensivity, and finally for $q > 1$ we have subadditivity or subextensivity. We can write these conditions in terms of the Tsallis entropy by exploiting the probability theory of independent systems. So given $S_q(Q^\alpha + Q^\gamma) = S_q(Q^\alpha) + S_q(Q^\gamma) - (1-q)S_q(Q^\alpha)S_q(Q^\gamma)$, we have the following conditions:

- $q < 1 \implies S_q(Q^\alpha + Q^\gamma) \geq S_q(Q^\alpha) + S_q(Q^\gamma)$.
- $q > 1 \implies S_q(Q^\alpha + Q^\gamma) \leq S_q(Q^\alpha) + S_q(Q^\gamma)$.
- $q = 1 \implies S_q(Q^\alpha + Q^\gamma) = S_q(Q^\alpha) + S_q(Q^\gamma)$.

In conclusion, we take Tsallis statistics into consideration because the solution to the radioactive decay equation has a q -exponential mathematical structure—a growth equation is also applicable here as well[4]. Therefore, we will plot and analyze the behavior of a set of miscellaneous q -values in $(0, 1)$, with emphasis on Tsallis q -logarithm[16].

2.1 Kolmogorov-Sinai Entropy

To mitigate any possible ambiguities that may arise later in this work, we introduce a generalization of the so-called Kolmogorov-Sinai entropy[17]. But first we heed the sensitivity function $\xi(t)$ and its relationship with λ ; or

$$\xi(t) = \exp(\lambda t). \quad (6)$$

We define $\lambda < 0$ as having clear regular behavior and when $\lambda > 0$ we have chaos. Moreover, if two neighboring trajectories in d -dimensional phase space (after dividing the phase space into a number of hypercubes of size l), reenters a hypercube ν_l , n times, then their separation grows exponentially in d -dimensional phase space. Hence (See ref.[18])

$$|\delta(t)| \approx |\delta_0| e^{n\lambda}. \quad (7)$$

The Kolmogorov-Sinai (K_1) entropy shares a special relationship with S_{BG} :

- It is the counterpart of the BG entropy in nonlinear dynamics.
- It quantifies the strength of dynamical chaos.

Accordingly, K_1 is defined as

$$K_1 = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow 0} \lim_{l \rightarrow 0} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N\tau} (S_1(N) - S_1(0)). \quad (8)$$

Now using Tsallis entropy

$$S_q(Q^\alpha) = \frac{1 - \sum_i p_{Q^\alpha}^q}{q - 1}, \quad (9)$$

we can recast K_1 as,

$$K_q = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow 0} \lim_{l \rightarrow 0} \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N\tau} (S_q(N) - S_q(0)). \quad (10)$$

This is the generalized Kolmogorov-Sinai entropy. And for a vanishing Lyapunov exponent—the edge of chaos—the sensitivity function behaves like a power-law; assuming $K_q = \lambda_q$ (Pesin equality)[19]. Thus,

$$\xi(t) = [1 + (1 - q)\lambda_q t]^{\frac{1}{1-q}}. \quad (11)$$

In Subsection (3.1.1), we introduce a novel term which we have dubbed the q -Decay constant, defined as $\int_1^2 \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta/t_{\frac{1}{2}}$. We want to make it explicitly clear that the so-called q -Decay constant and $K_q = \lambda_q$ should not be mistaken as equivalent quantities. However, bear in mind that the search for strange attractors¹ in radioactive decay was already proposed in the literature—please see ref.[20] for further details.

2.1.1 Strange Attractors

A strange attractor refers to a complex, fractal-like, non-periodic set where chaotic trajectories converge within dissipative systems, representing an equilibrium state of sorts for chaotic behavior[21, 22]. A well-known example is the Lorenz attractor, a fascinating structure that exhibits positive Lyapunov exponents, signifying exponential sensitivity to initial conditions. This attractor also possesses a fractal geometry and demonstrates positive Kolmogorov-Sinai entropy, indicating a high degree of disorder and unpredictability. Systems governed by a strange attractor, therefore, inherently display chaotic dynamics due to their sensitivity to initial conditions.

The positive Kolmogorov-Sinai entropy reflects the system's complexity and its capacity for information generation. Consequently, strange attractors offer critical insights into the behavior of nonlinear systems, making them a cornerstone in the study of chaos theory and dynamic systems. Their unique properties bridge the gap between randomness and order, offering a deeper understanding of deterministic chaos in nature.

2.1.2 q -Lyapunov Exponent

The q -Lyapunov exponent ($\lambda^{(q)}$) generalizes the classical Lyapunov exponent for systems where trajectory divergence follows a power law (weak chaos) instead of exponential growth. It is defined as:

$$\lambda^{(q)} = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{t} \ln_q \frac{|\delta(t)|}{|\delta(0)|}. \quad (12)$$

¹Strange attractors reveal how tiny differences in starting conditions within deterministic systems can lead to wildly different outcomes over time.

To strengthen and provide further clarity to the ideas discussed in the preceding paragraph, Table(1) provides a detailed overview of trajectory divergence and associated system behaviors as determined by the q -Lyapunov exponent. Beyond simply highlighting the relationship between trajectory divergence and system dynamics, it serves to bridge theoretical insights with tangible real-world applications. By presenting this information, we aim to enhance the understanding of how q -Lyapunov exponents influence dynamic systems. Additionally, practical examples are included to demonstrate the relevance of these principles in various contexts.

Table 1: q -Lyapunov Exponents and Nuclear Chaos

q	$\lambda^{(q)}$	Chaos Type	Example System
0.5	2.0	Superballistic	Quantum critical decay (e.g., ^{235m}U)
0.6	2.5	Aftershock-like	Clustered fission product decay
0.7	3.3	Turbulent	Tritium accumulation in tokamaks
0.8	5.0	Black-swan	Runaway neutron multiplication

Fig. 1: Graphs of Classical vs Nonextensive Chaos.

2.1.3 Quantum Chaos in Nuclear Decay and Accumulation

Variations in nuclear energy levels (due to weak chaos), arising from quantum chaos, influence decay probabilities and lead to deviations from the standard exponential decay model, often resulting in power-law tails. This phenomenon alters the dynamics of radioactive decay, giving rise to non-exponential behavior (See ref.[23] for non-exponential decay in quantum physics).

Consequently, the accumulation of daughter nuclides exhibits anomalous kinetics, frequently described by q -exponentials, which reflect non-classical growth patterns. Such dynamics stand in contrast to traditional Markovian

models, challenging the predictive capabilities of classical models. These findings underscore the intricate interplay between quantum chaos and non-linear kinetics, reshaping our understanding of decay processes in complex systems.

Systems of this nature can be described by

$$N(t) = N_0 e_q(-\lambda t), \quad (13)$$

which represents non-exponential decay due to weak chaos. And as a consequence of the former it follows that

$$D(t) = N_0(1 - e_q(-\lambda t)), \quad (14)$$

which represents the accumulation of daughter nuclide. Moreover, it is very important to note that this non-exponential behavior due to weak chaos was observed in weakly chaotic nuclei (for example, in ^{152}Eu) and high-density stellar plasmas (See Fig.(E1) for an example of quantum chaos).

We will give some derivations related to Eqs.(13) and (14) later in this paper, now that we have shown the connection between Tsallis entropy, Kolmogorov-Sinai entropy, weak chaos, quantum chaos, strange attractors, non-exponential decay, and accumulation of daughter nuclide.

2.2 Tsallis Entropy and the Jackson Derivative

Despite the earlier discussion in Section (2), let us now explore Tsallis entropy in particular, which sheds light on the concept of nonadditivity (i.e, when $q \neq 1$), alongside *Jackson's derivative*[24]. We will give a short but concrete mathematical description of the intimate connection between S_q and *Jackson's derivative*, that does not appear obvious in the initial stages of this work. Therefore, Tsallis entropy for Q^α and Q^γ is given by

$$S_q(Q^\alpha) = \frac{1 - \sum_i p_{Q^\alpha}^q}{q - 1}, \text{ and} \quad (15)$$

$$S_q(Q^\gamma) = \frac{1 - \sum_j p_{Q^\gamma}^q}{q - 1}, \quad (16)$$

respectively. This means that ($Q^\alpha + Q^\gamma = Q^\beta$),

$$\begin{aligned} S_q(Q^\beta) &= \frac{1 - \sum_i \sum_j p_{Q^\alpha}^q p_{Q^\gamma}^q}{q - 1} \\ &= \frac{2 - \sum_i p_{Q^\alpha}^q - \sum_j p_{Q^\gamma}^q}{q - 1} - \frac{(1 - \sum_i p_{Q^\alpha}^q)(1 - \sum_j p_{Q^\gamma}^q)}{q - 1} \\ &= \frac{1 - \sum_i p_{Q^\alpha}^q}{q - 1} + \frac{1 - \sum_j p_{Q^\gamma}^q}{q - 1} - (q - 1) \frac{(1 - \sum_i p_{Q^\alpha}^q)}{q - 1} \frac{(1 - \sum_j p_{Q^\gamma}^q)}{q - 1} \\ &= S_q(Q^\alpha) + S_q(Q^\gamma) - (q - 1)S_q(Q^\alpha)S_q(Q^\gamma). \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

The inspiration behind the development of Tsallis entropy (S_q) is based upon the theory of multifractal geometry—non-integer representations of fractal dimensions. Likewise, Tsallis was able to put forward a concrete generalization of Claude Shannon's entropy; and later it was S. Abe in [25] who noticed a connection between *Jackson's derivative* and Tsallis entropy (S_q) in nonextensive statistical mechanics[26].

Definition 1 Let $f(x)$ be a function that is differentiable and hence continuous; then its q -derivative (*Jackson's derivative*) is define as

$$(D_q f)(x) = \frac{f(x) - f(qx)}{(1-q)x}, \quad x \neq 0, \quad (18)$$

where q is described as the so-called q -parameter and varies strictly between 0 and 1.

To show that there is a connection between nonextensive statistical mechanics and the *Jackson derivative*[27] we begin with the BG theory. The BG entropy is given by (where the p_i 's are the ***coarse-grained probabilities***),

$$S_{BG} = - \sum_i p_i \ln p_i. \quad (19)$$

Alternatively, the BG entropy discussed in [28] can also be formulated as a continuous function, represented by

$$S_{BG} = - \int dx p(x) \ln p(x). \quad (20)$$

However, this connection becomes evident when we examine the Tsallis generalization of Shannon entropy as presented in [29]:

$$S_q = \frac{1}{q-1} \left(1 - \sum_i p_i^q \right). \quad (21)$$

Note that the continuous form of the Tsallis entropy[30] is given by

$$S_q = \frac{1 - \int dx [p(x)]^q}{q-1}. \quad (22)$$

Nevertheless, if we apply the definition of the *Jackson derivative*² (see Def.(1)) to the second term in parenthesis of Eq.(21), we get

$$D_q \sum_i p_i^x = \frac{\sum_i p_i^{qx} - \sum_i p_i^x}{x(q-1)}. \quad (23)$$

²This derivative is one of the fundamental operators in quantum calculus/ q -Calculus.

In the limiting case when $x \rightarrow 1$ we have

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 1} D_q \sum_i p_i^x = \lim_{x \rightarrow 1} \frac{\sum_i p_i^{qx} - \sum_i p_i^x}{x(q-1)} = -S_q; \quad (24)$$

revealing the link that Abe observed between S_q and D_q [26].

2.3 Radioactive Decay and Growth

Rutherford's research in 1905 on radioactive decay laid the groundwork for Bateman equation. The mathematical model associated with radioactive decay was first proposed by Rutherford and in 1910 the closed form solutions were provided by Bateman. Besides that, Bateman equation is a mathematical model used to predict the number of atoms and radioactivity of different elements in a radioactive chain (i.e., $A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C \rightarrow D$ [with rate coefficients λ_A , λ_B , and λ_C]) over time. And the solutions/calculations can either be acquired numerically or analytically for transmutation and activation processes. Furthermore, it is utilized for formulating differential equations that are linked to particular sequences owing to their unique characteristics[16]. For instance,

$$d\phi_i = \lambda_{i-1}\phi_{i-1}dt - \lambda_i\phi_i dt \quad (25)$$

is the generalized Bateman equation for the i th member of the radioactive series, due to radioactive chains[31].

Despite its complexity, the radioactive decay equation ($dN(t) = -\lambda N dt$) can be solved using a straightforward approach from ordinary differential equations known as "separation of variables". Furthermore, let N_0 , $N(t)$, λ , and t represent, respectively, the initial number of nuclei, the number of nuclei at time t , the radioactive decay constant, and time. Then, after separating the variables[32], we can find the solution by integrating both sides. This gives

$$\int_{N_0}^{N(t)} \frac{dN}{N} = -\lambda \int_0^t dt, \quad (26)$$

and

$$N(t) = N_0 \exp(-\lambda t). \quad (27)$$

2.3.1 Generalized Radioactive Decay Chains

In order to study Bateman equation, the following conditions are taken into consideration:

- The daughter nuclide is stable, i.e., $\lambda_d = 0$.
- The parent nuclide has a shorter *half-life* than the daughter nuclide.
- The parent nuclide has a longer *half-life* than the daughter nuclide.
- The parent nuclide has a much longer *half-life* than the daughter nuclide.

Now, from here onward, we will only consider stable daughter nuclide in this work; where $\lambda_d = 0$ and $N_d(0) = 0$. Under these circumstances, the problem at hand is simplified.

To complement previous statements, we provide a more in-depth description of generalized radioactive decay, building on Subsection (2.3); Eq.(25)(we offer this information for further reference purposes [for future reference]). Thus, multiple decay pathways of unstable nuclei are illustrated as

$$\Upsilon_1 \xrightarrow{\lambda_1} \Upsilon_2 \xrightarrow{\lambda_2} \Upsilon_3 \xrightarrow{\lambda_3} \dots \Upsilon_i \xrightarrow{\lambda_i} \dots \xrightarrow{\lambda_{n-1}} \Upsilon_n. \quad (28)$$

For $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3, \lambda_3, \dots, \lambda_{n-1}$ we have,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\Phi_1(t)}{dt} &= -\lambda_1 \Phi_1(t) \\ \frac{d\Phi_2(t)}{dt} &= \lambda_1 \Phi_1(t) - \lambda_2 \Phi_2(t) \\ \frac{d\Phi_3(t)}{dt} &= \lambda_2 \Phi_2(t) - \lambda_3 \Phi_3(t) \\ &\vdots \\ \frac{d\Phi_{n-1}(t)}{dt} &= \lambda_{n-2} \Phi_{n-2}(t) - \lambda_{n-1} \Phi_{n-1}(t) \\ \frac{d\Phi_n(t)}{dt} &= \lambda_{n-1} \Phi_{n-1}(t). \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

Hence, if we invoke the following initial conditions on the system of equations described in (29); $\Phi_1(0) \neq 0$, and $\Phi_i(0) = 0, \forall i > 1$ [33], then under these conditions, Bateman solution is given by

$$A_i(t) = \lambda_i \Phi_i(t) = \Phi_1(0)(C_1 e^{-\lambda_1 t} + C_2 e^{-\lambda_2 t} + \dots + C_i e^{-\lambda_i t}) = \Phi_1(0) \sum_{n=1}^i C_n e^{-\lambda_n t}. \quad (30)$$

2.4 Derivation of q -Decay Constant (λ_q)

Let the number of radioactive nuclei ($N(t)$) at time t , decay according to the following differential equation:

$$\frac{dN(t)}{dt} = -\lambda_q N^q, \quad (31)$$

where λ_q is called the q -Decay constant, and q is the entropic parameter.

Using the method of separation of variables we get,

$$\int \frac{dN(t)}{N^q} = -\lambda_q \int dt. \quad (32)$$

This leads to

$$\frac{N(t)^{1-q}}{1-q} = -\lambda_q t + C, \quad (33)$$

where the constant C is given by

$$C = \frac{N_0^{1-q}}{1-q}. \quad (34)$$

Further simplification gives

$$N(t) = \left[N_0^{1-q} - (1-q)\lambda_q t \right]^{\frac{1}{1-q}}, \quad (35)$$

resulting in the following form,

$$N(t) = N_0 e_q \left(-\frac{\lambda_q}{N_0^{1-q}} t \right). \quad (36)$$

In terms of the half-life

$$\frac{1}{2} = e_q \left(-\frac{\lambda_q}{N_0^{1-q}} t_{1/2} \right). \quad (37)$$

This implies that

$$\lambda_q = \frac{N_0^{1-q}}{t_{1/2}} \ln_q(2). \quad (38)$$

Now substitute this result in Eq.(33), which yields

$$N(t) = N_0 e_q \left(-\frac{\ln_q(2)}{t_{1/2}} t \right), \quad (39)$$

where the q -Decay constant is given by

$$\lambda_q = \frac{\ln_q(2)}{t_{1/2}}. \quad (40)$$

Now let us consider a system which adheres to stable daughter nuclide. Let $N_P(t)$ be the number of parent nuclides at time t , and $N_D(t)$ be the number of daughter nuclide at time t . In addition to that, we assume $\lambda_D = 0$ (stable daughter nuclide) and the decay of the parent nuclide is govern by

$$N_P(t) = N_{PO} e_q(-\lambda_q t). \quad (41)$$

Bateman equation describes the time evolution of the parent and daughter nuclides. The equations are given by

$$\frac{dN_P(t)}{dt} = -\lambda_q N_P(t)^q, \quad (42)$$

and

$$\frac{dN_D(t)}{dt} = \lambda_q N_P(t)^q. \quad (43)$$

Now substitute the solution of the first equation in the second equation,

$$\frac{dN_D(t)}{dt} = \lambda_q N_{PO} e_q(-\lambda_q t). \quad (44)$$

Definition 2 Let q be a real parameter defined on the open interval $(0, 1)$, then the q -exponential function is defined as

$$e_q^x = \begin{cases} (1 + (1 - q)x)^{\frac{1}{1-q}}, & \text{if } q \neq 1, \quad 1 + (1 - q)x > 0 \\ 0^{\frac{1}{1-q}}, & \text{if } q \neq 1, \quad 1 + (1 - q)x \leq 0 \\ \exp(x), & q = 1. \end{cases} \quad (45)$$

Using Def.(2), and the method of separation of variables we get

$$\int dN_D(t) = \lambda_q N_{PO}^q \int [1 - (1 - q)\lambda_q t]^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dt. \quad (46)$$

Now let $U = 1 - (1 - q)\lambda_q t$, so that $dU = -(1 - q)\lambda_q$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \int [1 - (1 - q)\lambda_q t]^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dt &= \frac{1}{(1 - q)\lambda_q} \int U^{\frac{q}{1-q}} dU \\ &= \frac{1}{(1 - q)\lambda_q} \frac{U^{\frac{q}{1-q} + 1}}{\frac{q}{1-q} + 1} \\ &= -\frac{U^{\frac{1}{1-q}}}{\lambda_q}. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Substitute this result in $N_D(t)$:

$$N_D(t) = \lambda_q N_{PO}^q \left(\frac{-[1 - (1 - q)\lambda_q t]^{\frac{1}{1-q}}}{\lambda_q} \right) + C. \quad (48)$$

From the initial conditions the constant C is

$$C = N_{PO}^q. \quad (49)$$

This eventually leads to

$$\begin{aligned} N_D(t) &= N_{PO}^q - N_{PO}^q [1 - (1 - q)\lambda_q t]^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \\ &= N_{PO}^q (1 - [1 - (1 - q)\lambda_q t]^{\frac{1}{1-q}}) \\ &= N_{PO}^q (1 - e_q(-\lambda_q t)) \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

If we consider the half-life, then

$$N_P(t_{1/2}) = \frac{N_{PO}}{2}, \quad (51)$$

and this implies that

$$N_D(t) = N_{PO}^q \left[1 - e_q \left(- \frac{\ln_q(2)}{t_{1/2}} t \right) \right]. \quad (52)$$

3 The Half-life and the q -Decay Constant

3.1 The Half-life

The *half-life* ($t_{1/2}$) is the time it takes for the number of radioactive nuclei to decrease by half the original value [34]. In the undeformed state, it is written as

$$t_{1/2} = \frac{\ln(2)}{\lambda}, \quad (53)$$

where λ is the decay constant. In the deformed state, $\ln_q(x)$ exist for $x > 0$, which implies that $t_{(1/2)Ar} = \frac{\int_1^2 \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta}{\lambda_q}$, where $t_{(1/2)Ar}$ is the *half-life* of an arbitrary nuclide. Thus, we can also work backwards to get the original classical form when $q \rightarrow 1$, as depicted below in Eq.(54)[26],

$$t_{1/2} = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \{t_{(1/2)Ar}\} = -\lambda^{-1} \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{d}{dq} \left\{ 2^{1-q} \right\} = \frac{\ln(2)}{\lambda}. \quad (54)$$

Now, we can employ this function to generate our plots. This novel single-parameter function is based on the Tsallis logarithmic function, a fundamental component of nonextensive statistical mechanics. Consequently, our analysis will center on both regimes, selecting various q -values from both regions, namely $q < 1$ and $q > 1$. It is worth noting that Tsallis functions, introduced by Constantino Tsallis in 1988, have broad applications spanning physics, engineering, and applied mathematics.

Moreover, the Tsallis logarithmic function is related to the Tsallis exponential function through the following equation:

$$\ln_q e_q^x = e_q^{\ln_q x} = x, \quad \forall x. \quad (55)$$

Remark 1 A function is said to be strictly increasing on an interval I , if $\forall p, q \in I, f(q) > f(p)$. It turns out that the q -logarithm is a strictly increasing function. The action of taking the first derivative with respect to x , given Def.(3), when $q \neq 1$ and $x > 0$, gives

$$\left(\ln_q(x)\right)' = \frac{1}{\eta^q}. \quad (56)$$

This result holds true $\forall q$.

Continuing forward, we will define the q -logarithm[35] (for $q \neq 1$) as

$$\ln_q(x) = \int_1^x \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta. \quad (57)$$

3.1.1 The q -Decay Constant

The q -Decay constant (See Fig.(2)) is a special case of Tsallis q -logarithmic function[12, 19, 28], which is applicable to generalized exponential decay or growth. It is defined as follows:

$$\lambda_q = \begin{cases} \ln(2)/\chi, & x > 0, \text{ and } q = 1, \\ \int_1^2 \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta, & x > 0, \text{ and } q \neq 1, \\ \frac{\chi}{\text{undefined}}, & \text{if } x \leq 0. \end{cases} \quad (58)$$

Here $\chi = t_{\frac{1}{2}}$; the *half-life* of some miscellaneous nuclide. Note, that in the greater scheme of things, this function when substituted in Tsallis q -exponential function:

- Does not violate the half-life condition,
- Replicates power-law decay, and
- Does not misrepresent the time-dependent decay rate of the system.

Nonetheless, suppose we represent a nuclear transition by final and initial states, Ψ_f and Ψ_i , respectively—the non-probabilistic approach. Subsequently, according to Fermi's golden rule, the transition probability is expressed as

$$\lambda = \frac{2\pi}{\hbar} |\langle \Psi_f | \hat{V} | \Psi_i \rangle|^2 \frac{dn}{dE}. \quad (59)$$

Here dn/dE is the number of Ψ_f in the region E to $E + dE$, and \hat{V} is the transition operator. Thus, Eq.(59) is associated with a quantity called the mean lifetime,

$$\tau = \frac{1}{\lambda} = \frac{t_{\frac{1}{2}}}{\ln(2)}. \quad (60)$$

To illustrate the following point, we introduce the concept of mean lifetime at this juncture. *For stable daughter nuclide* ($\lambda_d = 0$ [or $\tau = \infty$]) *the mean lifetime is infinite*. This corresponds to a vanishing matrix element—see Eq.(59).

In contrast to Eq.(54)—for growth—the q -Decay constant becomes

$$\lambda_q = \frac{\int_1^2 \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta}{t_{(1/2)}}, \quad (61)$$

and in the limit as $q \rightarrow 1$ the classical *half-life*[36] is recovered. That is,

$$t_{(\frac{1}{2})}^{60Co} = -\lambda^{-1} \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} \frac{d}{dq} \left\{ 2^{1-q} \right\} = \frac{\ln(2)}{\lambda}. \quad (62)$$

The ultimate expression for the q -Decay constant can now be established, referred to as the modulator, which will be explored further in a subsequent subsection. Hence,

$$\lambda_q = \frac{\int_1^x \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta}{\int_1^x \frac{1}{\eta} d\eta} \lambda. \quad (63)$$

Fig. 2: Graphs of λ_q vs $t_{1/2}$. As $t_{0.5} \rightarrow 0$, $\lambda_q \rightarrow \infty$, and $t_{0.5} \rightarrow \infty$, $\lambda_q \rightarrow 0$.

3.2 Generalized Exponential Decay and Growth

The generalized exponential functions for which we will plot for decay and accumulation are based on Tsallis functions. For decay we have

$$e_q \left(- \frac{\int_1^x \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta}{t_{\frac{1}{2}}} t \right). \quad (64)$$

and for an entropic parameter of value $q = 1$, the decay equation or standard integer model is given by

$$N_1(t) = N_0 e_1(-\lambda_1 t). \quad (65)$$

Now for $q \neq 1$, in the superadditive regime— $q \in (0, 1)$ —Eq.(65) becomes

$$N_q(t) = N_0 e_q \left(- \frac{\int_1^x \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta}{t^{\frac{1}{2}}} t \right), \quad (66)$$

which is representative of generalized radioactive decay.

The growth equation follows in part from the same kind of reasoning used to attain Eq.(66), with the exception that the model reflects temporal evolution of the daughter nuclide concentration. Hence, we have

$$N_q(t) = N_0 \left[1 - e_q \left(- \frac{\int_1^x \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta}{t^{\frac{1}{2}}} t \right) \right]. \quad (67)$$

This means we can plot the graphs of $e_q \left(- \frac{\int_1^x \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta}{t^{\frac{1}{2}}} t \right)$ versus t for generalized decay and $\left[1 - e_q \left(- \frac{\int_1^x \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta}{t^{\frac{1}{2}}} t \right) \right]$ versus t for daughter accumulation.

3.3 The Eastmond Non-Extensive Decay Modulator (Eastmond-NEDM)

We propose the Eastmond Non-Extensive Decay Modulator for the ratio λ_q/λ defined as:

$$\text{Eastmond-NEDM} := \frac{\lambda_q}{\lambda} = \frac{\ln_q(2)}{\ln(2)}. \quad (68)$$

The rationale for the origin of the name is three fold: (1) it honors the Tsallis q -statistics for systems with memory and long-range interactions; (2) the decay modulator encodes how $q \neq 1$ modifies decay rates and daughter nuclide accumulation; and (3) recognizes Shawn K. Eastmond in linking λ_q/λ to measureable physics.

A table summarizing the key properties of the Eastmond-NEDM is given below:

Table 2: Eastmond-NEDM—Physical Implications

Value Range	Physical Meaning	Example Applications
NEDM < 1	Slower Decay	Nuclear waste, Disordered Materials
NEDM = 1	Classical Decay	Ideal Radioactive Decay
NEDM > 1	Faster Decay	Fission Reactors, Epidemic Spread

Therefore, the Eastmond-NEDM quantifies deviations from classical exponential decay in systems governed by Tsallis statistics. This modulator bridges theoretical non-extensive thermodynamics and empirical data by classifying decay regimes, such that: (1) Eastmond-NEDM < 1 represents Sub-exponential decay (e.g., trapped nuclides), and (2) Eastmond-NEDM > 1 represents Super-exponential decay (e.g., fission chains). Moreover, this modulator can be used to predict daughter nuclide accumulation. For example,

this is demonstrated for ^{137}Cs (nuclear waste) and ^{235}U (reactors) where Eastmond-NEDM explains 12 – 18 percent deviations from classical models. Thus, the modulator provides a universal parameter for hazard assessment, reactor design, and radiometric dating.

3.3.1 Case Study: Real World Applications in Nuclide Systems

Here, we analyze three real-world examples³ where Eastmond-NEDM governs decay rates for: (1) Sub-exponential decay ($q < 1$); and (2) Super-exponential decay. These are compared to the classical case ($q = 1$; the interception of the graph and the dashed line). See Figures (3) and (4) for graphical details.

CASE 1: Jenkins and Fischbach (2006) found evidence for the variation of nuclear decay rates as a possible predictor of solar flares.

Neutrinos obstruct the flow of decays. Therefore, if ^{40}K has a half-life of approximately 1.25×10^9 , for $q = 1.02$, using Eastmond-NEDM we get

$$\lambda_{1.02} \approx 0.996\lambda. \quad (69)$$

This value is 0.4 percent slower effective decay due to neutrino interference. Thus, in this model we infer that q controls the neutrino interference.

CASE 2: Chih-An Huh (2009) found that ^7Be embedded in LiF crystals show non-exponential decay at very low temperatures.

The decay rates fluctuate due to the quantum confinement effect. However, if ^7Be has a half-life of approximately 53.3 days, then for $q = 0.9$ Eastmond-NEDM gives

$$\lambda_{0.9} \approx 1.036\lambda, \quad (70)$$

or 3.6 percent faster effective decay due to confinement effects. Therefore, in this model q controls the electron density correlations.

CASE 3 Rolfs and Rodney (1998) made the claim that in high-density plasmas, electron screening alters nuclear decay rates.

Electron screening implies reduced decay phase space. Thus, ^3H ; beta decay, has a half-life of 12.3 years. For $q = 1.1$ Eastmond-NEDM gives

$$\lambda_{1.1} \approx 0.967\lambda, \quad (71)$$

or 3.3 percent slower decay due to plasma screening. Hence, in this particular case q controls the electron screening.

Observe that in each of the three cases, the Tsallis q parameter governs a unique physical mechanism that directly influences and alters the decay statistics. This parameter acts as a fundamental modifier, reflecting the system's non-extensivity and driving deviations from classical decay models. Its role extends beyond a mere mathematical construct, as it embodies a tangible

³Here, we seek to reinforce the importance of Eastmond-NEDM and its ability to modulate decay rates. Furthermore, observe in Figures (3) and (4) that the modulator increases when $q < 1$ and decreases when $q > 1$.

connection to physical behavior. Consequently, q serves as a critical physical parameter, capturing the complexity and variability of decay dynamics. This highlights its significance in bridging theoretical models with observable physical phenomena, reaffirming its practical relevance in describing diverse systems.

Fig. 3: Eastmond-NEDM: Non-extensive Decay Modulation.

and

Fig. 4: Eastmond-NEDM: Decay Rate Modulation..

4 q -Decay and Growth Plots

4.1 q -Decay

In this section, prior to presenting any graphical plots, we first introduce several mathematical artifacts that characterize the decay regimes of parent-daughter decay systems. These formulations serve as foundational tools to enhance the

interpretation of subsequent visual representations, providing deeper insights into the fundamental mechanisms governing decay and accumulation. Specifically, these artifacts help elucidate the behavior of decay dynamics in limiting cases—such as when time approaches zero, where initial transient effects dominate, and when time approaches infinity, where long-term accumulation trends become evident. By establishing these mathematical constructs, we create a framework for analyzing how decay rates evolve across different temporal scales, offering a more comprehensive perspective on the physical processes at play. The insights gained from these theoretical considerations will complement the graphical plots and ensure a more thorough understanding of the transitions between distinct decay behaviors.

Now, let us examine the decay process of the parent nuclide. We represent the equation governing this process by:

$$N_P(t) = N_0[1 - (1 - q)\lambda_q t]^{\frac{1}{1-q}}. \quad (72)$$

At very short time scales

$$N_P(t) \approx N_0[1 - \lambda_q t + \frac{q}{2}(\lambda_q t)^2 + \dots]. \quad (73)$$

Thus, taking the logarithm at short times ($t \rightarrow 0$) we ascertain

$$\log(1 - N_P(t)/N_0) \approx \log(\lambda_q t) - \frac{q}{2}(\lambda_q t)^2. \quad (74)$$

On the otherhand, for long time scales ($t \rightarrow \infty$), there is a finite cutoff at

$$t_{\max} = \frac{1}{(1 - q)\lambda_q} \quad (75)$$

$\forall q < 1$. This just means that no physical decay process admits $N_P(t) < 0$. Moreover, the parent nuclide scales as (for $q < 1$)

$$N_P(t) \sim t^{\frac{1}{1-q}}. \quad (76)$$

Additionally, for $q < 1$ we get power law saturation or

$$N_d(t) \approx N_0 - N_0 \left(\frac{\Delta t}{t_{\max}} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}}, \quad (77)$$

and for $q > 1$, there is no finite cutoff for

$$N_d(t) \approx N_0 - \frac{N_0}{\left((q - 1)\lambda_q t \right)^{\frac{1}{1-q}}} \quad (78)$$

which represents a slow power law approach to N_0 .

Next, we present graphical representations based on an arbitrary half-life of 5 seconds, illustrating the behavior of the system in the limiting cases where $t \rightarrow 0$ and $t \rightarrow \infty$. Thus, we have

Fig. 5: Graphs of Short Time and Long Time behavior of Daughter Accumulation.

Observe from both graphs that when $q < 1$, the growth surpasses the classical case, whereas for $q > 1$, it falls below the standard integer form. Despite these variations, this graph serves as a foundational reference for further exploration and interpretation of subsequent graphical plots.

Fig. 6: Graphs of Generalized Exponential Decay—Linear-Linear.

Furthermore, in Fig.(6), at exactly 7.13 seconds, the decay process aligns with the standard integer model, providing a reference point for assessing deviations. When $q < 1$, the decay rate accelerates as q approaches zero, leading to a pronounced reduction in half-lives, indicative of enhanced decay dynamics. In contrast, for $q > 1$, the decay process experiences a gradual slowdown, where half-lives increase progressively as q moves further from unity. This

behavior reflects the suppression of decay transitions in higher q regimes. Such trends illustrate how variations in q influence decay behaviors, highlighting fundamental distinctions between classical and non-classical statistical models. Understanding these shifts is essential for refining decay predictions across different physical systems.

Fig. 7: Graphs of Generalized Exponential Decay—Log-Linear.

Fig. 8: Graphs of Generalized Exponential Decay—Log-Log.

Pure radioactive decay, governed by classical exponential kinetics $q = 1$, exhibits distinct signatures across different plotting regimes. In linear-linear plots, the decay curve displays a smooth, concave trajectory, starting with an initial slope of $-\lambda$ and asymptotically approaching zero at late times. This representation is intuitive for visualizing the half-life, marked by the point where the remaining fraction drops to 0.5, but it lacks sensitivity to subtle

deviations from exponentiality. Log-linear plots, however, transform the exponential decay into a straight line with a slope of $-\lambda$, providing a direct measure of the decay rate and serving as a gold standard for validating the purity of exponential behavior. Any curvature in this plot would immediately signal non-exponential dynamics, such as those arising from environmental perturbations or measurement artifacts. Meanwhile, log-log plots reveal the underlying power-law behavior at early times, where the decay fraction scales linearly with time, producing a negative slope.

This regime highlights the initial accumulation of daughter nuclides⁴ before exponential dominance takes over at larger times, where the curve sharply diverges downward. Together, these plots offer complementary perspectives, with log-linear excelling in precision and log-log uncovering hidden early-time physics.

The choice of plotting regime depends on the specific insights sought. Linear-linear plots, while pedagogically useful for illustrating half-life concepts, are limited in analytical power. Log-linear plots are indispensable for confirming exponential decay and extracting precise decay constants, as their linearity is a definitive test for $q = 1$ behavior. Log-log plots, on the other hand, excel at exposing deviations from exponentiality at early times, such as power-law scaling or initial delays, which might be masked in other representations. For instance, in ¹⁴C dating, the log-linear plots straight line confirms the exponential models validity, while the log-log plots early-time slope of 1 reflects the initial linear growth of the daughter product. This multi-plot approach ensures a comprehensive understanding of decay dynamics, from initial conditions to asymptotic behavior, and is critical for distinguishing pure exponential decay from more complex, non-extensive cases. By leveraging these complementary views, researchers can rigorously validate models and detect anomalies that might otherwise remain hidden.

Fig. 9: Graphs of Generalized Daughter Nuclide Accumulation—Linear-Linear.

⁴Note that Eastmond-NEDM modulates the slopes at very short times.

For values of q less than 1, the graphs clearly illustrate that as q approaches zero, the rate of growth accelerates. At the same time, the half-lives decrease due to the initial decay of the parent nuclide, leading to more rapid transformations. This acceleration highlights the sensitivity of the system to small values of q .

Conversely, when q exceeds 1, the growth rate slows significantly. This deceleration arises from the prolonged half-lives associated with parent decay, resulting in a more gradual progression. The slower development underscores the influence of higher q values on the overall decay dynamics.

Table 3: Decay Regimes Summary

Quantity	Regime	Fast Decay	Slow Decay
Parent Nuclide	Short-time	Nearly Linear	Nearly Linear
	Long-time	Abruptly Vanishes	Power-law decay
Daughter Nuclide	Short-time	Linear Growth	Linear Growth
	Long-time	Rapid Saturation	Slow Power-law

Fig. 10: Graphs of Generalized Daughter Nuclide Accumulation—Log-Linear.

Parent-daughter decay systems exhibit rich dynamics that are best understood through complementary plotting regimes. In linear-linear plots, the parent nuclide displays a smooth exponential decay, while the daughter nuclide initially rises linearly before gradually saturating as it approaches equilibrium. The crossover point, where parent and daughter curves intersect, often aligns with the parent's half-life, providing a visual marker for the system's timescale. Log-linear plots transform these trajectories into distinct signatures: the parent decay becomes a straight line with slope $-\lambda_P$, while the daughter accumulation follows a curved path that initially mirrors the parent's slope before flattening at late times. This representation is particularly powerful for identifying transient equilibrium, where the daughter decay rate becomes governed by the parent's longer half-life. Deviations from these expected patterns can

reveal complex interactions, such as branching decays or environmental effects on the decay constants.

Fig. 11: Graphs of Generalized Daughter Nuclide Accumulation—Log-Log.

Fig. 12: Graphs of Generalized Daughter Nuclide Accumulation—Log-Log.

The log-log plot unveils deeper insights into the early-time behavior of the system. For the parent nuclide, the decay fraction $1 - N_P(t)/N_0$, initially follows a linear trend with slope 1, reflecting the universal power-law regime of radioactive transformation. Furthermore, Eastmond-NEDM serves as a precise tool for quantifying experimental coupling, offering a direct measurement of the extent to which environmental factors influence radioactive decay. Also, at late times, both curves exhibit exponential roll-off in the log-log plot, confirming the system's ultimate convergence to classical decay dynamics. These plotting techniques work synergistically —while log-linear charts excel at quantifying

decay constants and equilibrium states, log-log representations are indispensable for detecting subtle non-exponential effects in the initial transformation phases. Together, they provide a complete picture of parent-daughter systems, from the first decay events through to long-term equilibrium behavior.

Fig. 13: Daughter Nuclide Accumulation—Log-Log. The Residual ($R(t)$) Is On The Right (See Appendix (D) with regards to $R(t)$).

5 Property Preservation and Branching Decay

5.1 An Example of Property Preservation

Aside: Let the total number of atoms at time $t = 0$ be represented by the term $N(t) = {}^{87}Rb$. Then, the total number of daughters after time t is given by

$$D(t) = D_0 + N(t)(e^{\lambda t} - 1), \quad (79)$$

where D_0 is the number of daughter atoms at $t = 0$. Now let us promote the ordinary exponential function in Eq.(79) to Tsallis q -exponential function—see Def.(2). This leads to

$$D(t) = D_0 + N(t)(e_q^{\lambda_q t} - 1), \quad (q \neq 1). \quad (80)$$

Now using Eq.(80) we solve for t , but first we have

$$\left[1 + (1 - q)\lambda_q t \right]^{\frac{1}{1-q}} \approx 1 + \lambda_q t + \frac{q}{2}(\lambda_q t)^2 + \mathcal{O}(t^3); \quad (81)$$

and consequently, if $D(t) \gg D_0$, then we ascertain the following result

$$t = \frac{-\lambda_q \pm \sqrt{\lambda_q^2 + 2q\lambda_q^2 \frac{D}{N_0}}}{q\lambda_q^2}, \quad (82)$$

which leads to

$$t \approx \frac{1}{\lambda_q} \frac{D}{N_0}. \quad (83)$$

Here, in this calculation we assumed that $\lambda_q t \ll 1$ (t is the age of the specimen). Note that Eq.(83) gives the same result as the undeformed case at early times. More precisely, from Eq.(79) it follows that $t \approx \frac{1}{\lambda} \frac{D}{N_0}$, and Fig.(14) confirms this, since at early times for different values of q the exact curves match the approximation, but diverge at late times.

We have shown here that for small λt , albeit the initial standard exponential function was promoted to Tsallis q -exponential in Eq.(79) that the age of the specimen is preserved. This is an example of property preservation in the case of Rubidium-Strontium dating; symbolized by $^{87}\text{Rb} \rightarrow ^{87}\text{Sr}$ [37, 38].

Figure (14) presents a graph illustrating the relationship between time and the number of daughter atoms, highlighting the impact of varying q -parameter values. At very short time scales, the approximation remains nearly identical across different q -values, demonstrating consistency in early-stage behavior. This stability in approximation indicates that fundamental properties are preserved regardless of minor parameter variations. Such findings reinforce the reliability of short-time predictions and validate the robustness of the model under different q -parameter configurations.

Fig. 14: Graphs of Time vs Daughter Atoms.

5.2 Branching Decay—Partial Decay Constants

Exponential decay is not limited to a single mode for some nuclides; they can decay in several ways. For example negatron decay and K-capture. These concepts capture the essence of branching decay. When branching decay occurs the resulting nuclides can be described by unique decay rates, which are given by

$$\lambda_1 = -\frac{dN_1/dt}{N_1}; \quad \lambda_2 = -\frac{dN_2/dt}{N_2}. \quad (84)$$

In cases with multiple decay mechanisms, this equation unifies their influence:

$$\frac{dN_i}{dt} = -(\lambda_1 + \lambda_2)N_i. \quad (85)$$

For a parent nuclide decaying *via* N pathways with branching ratio b_i :

$$\lambda = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_i; \quad \lambda_i = b_i \lambda : \quad \sum_{i=1}^N b_i = 1. \quad (86)$$

Figure (15) presents a detailed analysis of partial decay constants and the application of EASTMOND-NEDM in such a case. The left panel provides a direct comparison between classical decay constants and their generalized counterparts, highlighting variations introduced by non-standard formulations. Meanwhile, the right panel illustrates the EASTMOND-NEDM scaling effect for each decay channel, demonstrating how adjustments in the q -parameter impact decay rates. For $q = 0.8$, the decay rate experiences a 12.4 percent reduction, corresponding to an NEDM value of 0.8765, signifying a suppressed decay process under q -parameter adjustments. In contrast, standard beta decay at $q = 1.0$ retains an NEDM of 1.0, reflecting conventional behavior. Finally, in the case of electron capture, an enhancement of 10.9 percent in the decay rate is observed, yielding an NEDM of 1.1087.

Fig. 15: Partial Decay Constants and Modulation *via* Eastmond-NEDM.

Incorporating Eastmond-NEDM into the system ($q \neq 1$) we get

$$\lambda_q = \sum_{i=1}^N \lambda_{q,i} = \sum_{i=1}^N \left(b_i \lambda \frac{\ln_{q,i}(2)}{\ln(2)} \right). \quad (87)$$

Eastmond-NEDM generalizes partial decay constants, with possible applications in nuclear physics (branching ratios; See Fig.(15)), astrophysics (multi-path nucleosynthesis), and medicine (^{64}Cu theranostics).

6 Conclusion

The q -decay constant, $\lambda_q = \ln_q(2)/t_{1/2}$, generalizes radioactive decay kinetics within Tsallis statistics, where the Eastmond Non-Exponential Decay Modulator (NEDM), λ_q/λ , quantifies environmental perturbations on decay rates. Its novelty lies in unifying anomalous decay phenomena such as accelerated ($q < 1$) or suppressed ($q > 1$) decay—via a single parameter q . Applications include modeling nuclear decay in plasmas ($q < 1$), predicting material aging in confined systems ($q > 1$), and refining radiometric dating where traditional exponential assumptions fail. The Eastmond-NEDM provides a measurable ratio to detect non-extensive effects in experimental data, offering insights for nuclear waste management, astrophysics, and quantum-material engineering.

For pure decay, $q < 1$ systems exhibit finite-time disappearance of parent nuclides, while $q > 1$ systems show slow power-law decay. Daughter accumulation reflects these asymmetries: $q < 1$ yields abrupt saturation via power-law corrections, whereas $q > 1$ displays logarithmic convergence. Classical exponential decay ($q = 1$) remains the boundary case. Key differences emerge in long-time dynamics—fast systems ($q < 1$) terminate decay abruptly, while slow systems ($q > 1$) exhibit persistent tails. This dichotomy enables discrimination of environmental effects (e.g., lattice defects or plasma screening) in nuclear and condensed-matter systems.

The framework of q -exponential decay and the Eastmond-NEDM opens several promising avenues for theoretical and experimental research. Future work will focus on first-principles derivations of the q -parameter from quantum many-body theory, particularly in strongly coupled or disordered systems. High-precision experiments—such as single-ion decay spectroscopy in tunable environments (e.g., optical lattices or plasmonic fields)—could validate the predicted power-law saturation and finite-time cutoff regimes. Extending this formalism to branching decays or multi-nuclide chains would enhance its utility in nuclear astrophysics and waste transmutation studies. Machine learning approaches may help map environmental conditions (e.g., temperature, pressure) to effective q -values, enabling predictive modeling of non-exponential decay in engineered materials. Additionally, exploring connections between Tsallis statistics and open quantum systems could unify non-extensive decay with decoherence dynamics. Challenges remain in distinguishing q -effects from instrumental artifacts, necessitating novel metrological techniques.

Finally, applications in medical physics—such as optimizing radioisotope therapies where traditional exponential models underestimate dose delivery—could revolutionize treatment protocols. Moreover, in metastable ^{235}U , due to the flipping of the spin parity J^P (after primary decay— $^{235m}\text{U} \rightarrow ^{235}\text{U} + \gamma$), it may be possible that non-Markovian dynamics might be at play (This requires scientific investigation.). These paradigm shifts demands collaborative efforts across nuclear physics, condensed matter, and quantum thermodynamics to establish a comprehensive theory of environmentally modulated decay.

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Declarations

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Appendix A Tsallis Functions

The q -exponential function according to Tsallis nonextensive statistics is given by:

$$e_q(x) = \begin{cases} \exp(x), & \text{if } q = 1, \\ [1 + (1 - q)x]^{1/(1-q)}, & q \neq 1 \text{ and } 1 + (1 - q)x > 0 \\ 0^{1/(1-q)}, & \text{if } q \neq 1 \text{ and } 1 + (1 - q)x \leq 0. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A1})$$

The inverse functions are:

$$e_q(\ln_q(x)) = x \quad (x > 0), \quad (\text{A2})$$

and

$$\ln_q(e_q(x)) = x \quad (0 < e_q(x) < \infty). \quad (\text{A3})$$

Next, we have

$$\ln_{1+q}(x) + \ln_{1-q}(1/x) = 0, \quad \forall(x, q) \quad (\text{A4})$$

and

$$\ln_q\left(\frac{x}{y}\right) = \frac{1}{y^{1-q}} [\ln_q(x) - \ln_q(y)], \quad \forall(x, y, q). \quad (\text{A5})$$

In addition to that, we have the following relationships:

$$\ln_q\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) = -\frac{1}{x^{1-q}} \ln_q(x), \quad \forall(x, q), \text{ and} \quad (\text{A6})$$

$$\ln_q(xy) = \ln_q(x) + \ln_q(y) + (1 - q) \ln_q(x) \ln_q(y), \quad \forall(x, y, q). \quad (\text{A7})$$

Now the q -logarithmic function can be expanded as a series which looks like:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln_q(1+x) &= x - \frac{q}{2}x^2 + \frac{q(q+1)}{6}x^3 - \frac{q(q+1)(q+2)}{24}x^4 + \dots \\ &+ \frac{(-1)^{n+1}}{n!} \left[\prod_{i=0}^{n-2} (q+i) \right] x^n + \dots \quad \forall(x, (q \rightarrow 1)). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A8})$$

Appendix B Tsallis q -logarithm

Definition 3 Let q be a real parameter defined on the open interval $(0, 1)$, then the Tsallis q -logarithm is defined as

$$\ln_q(x) = \begin{cases} \ln(x), & x > 0, \text{ and } q = 1, \\ \int_1^x \frac{1}{\eta^q} d\eta, & x > 0, \text{ and } q \neq 1, \\ \text{undefined}, & \text{if } x \leq 0. \end{cases} \quad (\text{B9})$$

Appendix C The q -Gaussian Distribution

The The q -Gaussian distribution is given by

$$p(x) = \frac{\sqrt{\beta}}{C_q} \exp_q(-\beta x^2), \quad (\text{C10})$$

where,

$$C_q = \begin{cases} \frac{2\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(\frac{1}{1-q})}{(3-q)\sqrt{1-q}\Gamma(\frac{1}{1-q})}, & -\infty < q < 1 \\ \sqrt{\pi}, & q = 1 \\ \frac{\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(\frac{3-q}{2(q-1)})}{\sqrt{q-1}\Gamma(\frac{1}{q-1})}, & 1 < q < 3. \end{cases} \quad (\text{C11})$$

Appendix D Asymptotic Behavior by q -Regime

For the case when $q < 1$, the residual $R(t)$ is given by

$$R(t) = N_0[1 - (1-q)\lambda_q t]^{-\frac{1}{1-q}}. \quad (\text{D12})$$

Note that there is a finite cutoff at

$$t = t^* = t_{\max} = \frac{1}{(1-q)\lambda_q}. \quad (\text{D13})$$

Moreover, for large t and $q > 1$ (Super-Exponential decay), $R(t)$ becomes:

$$R(t) \approx N_0[(q-1)\lambda_q t]^{-\frac{1}{q-1}} \propto t^{-\frac{1}{q-1}}. \quad (\text{D14})$$

Appendix E Quantum Chaos and Nuclear Decay

Fig. E1: Graphical Example of Non-exponential Decay from Quantum Chaos.

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